

CLOUD SECURITY AND RESILIENCE: PRINCIPLES AND BEST PRACTICES

¹Onuora, A. C., ²Emereonye, G. I., ³Egwu-Ewah, R. I., ⁴Nnaji, D. I.

¹aconuora@akanuibiampoly.edu.ng, ²egoodluck@live.com, ³rita.janet@yahoo.com,
⁴david2405daniel@yahoo.com

^{1,2,3,4} Department of Computer Science

Akanu Ibiyam Federal Polytechnic Unwana

Abstract

The rise in the demand for cloud computing services has made it a thing of importance to make its security and resilience an importance topic. Cloud computing offers substantial benefits to its users: the ability to store and access massive amounts of data, on-demand delivery of computing services, the capability to widely share information, and the scalability of resource usage. Every business patronizing the cloud should be assured that its investment in migrating to the cloud is worthwhile. This Paper presents overview of Cloud Computing, its efficient architectures and applications. Also, several important features and challenges for cloud computing environments including availability, security and resilience was x-rayed. Finally, Principles and best practices for a secured and a resilient cloud were also considered.

Keywords: *Cloud computing, Resilience, Network security, Visualization, Iaas, Paas, Saas, Security tools, software resources, service provider.*

1.0 Introduction

Cloud computing is a large-scale distributed computing paradigm. It is the provision of all kinds of shared computing resources such as information, software, storage capacities and other infrastructures over the internet. It enables resource sharing, facilitates scalability and handles managed computing services delivered on demand over networks. Its users need not to buy infrastructure, software, resources, as a result saving a large amount of expenditure. Cloud basically provides services through a third party where users can rent or pay per use. This will save a lot of money and provides a greater flexibility to move from one service to another service (Hisham *et al*, 2012).

However, Cloud computing services are delivered on demand and pay-per-use via internet web browser protocols (Hypertext Transfer Protocols (HTTP) and HTTPS). They are configured dynamically for service delivery based on contractual agreements between cloud service provider and users (tenants). Corporations, governments and academic institutions are

actively considering the adoption of cloud computing services to lower costs, improve performance, increase storage capacity, provide interoperability, and reduce power consumption (green IT).

Consequently, cloud computing is a collection of sources in order to enable resource sharing in terms of scalability, managed computing services that are delivered on demand over the network. The cloud computing definition of National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) includes five essential features, three service models and four deployment models. The five essential features are resource pooling, broad network access, rapid elasticity and scalability, metered services (pay per use), on demand service. The three service models are Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), Software as a Service (SaaS); the four deployment models are community cloud, public cloud, private cloud and hybrid cloud. In a cloud computing environment, each of these models has their own significant services different from each other. (Peter and Grance, 2011).

Cloud computing is emerging day by day. People are using its services very frequently and they don't have any other alternative for its services. But users are unaware about the security and privacy concerns in a cloud environment. Since cloud computing is distributed in nature, supports multi-user and multi-domain platform, it is more prone to security threats. Security threats can be in terms of intrusion prospects and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks. Organizations need to provide firewalls, intrusion detection and prevention techniques, authentication, encryption and other powerful hardware and software protection to secure the stored data. Attackers try to find loopholes for breaking security. Attacks that originate from internal sources are called internal attacks. It includes unauthorized access of internal user. Attacks that originates from external sources are called external attacks

Although many organizations are considering cloud computing due to its many advantages, this outsourcing makes it difficult to maintain data integrity and privacy, support data and service availability, and demonstrate compliance. The complex nature of cloud computing means that cloud service providers, need to be mindful that things can go wrong – it's not a case of 'if' it's strictly a matter of 'when'. Cloud providers need to design and build their services in such a way to maximize the reliability of the service and minimize the impact to customers when things do go wrong. A key facet of this approach is business continuity, or ensuring that critical business functions continue to be available, even in the event of a catastrophe, that is resiliency.

2.0 Resilience in the Cloud

In cloud computing, resilience is the ability to provide and maintain an acceptable level of service in the face of faults and challenges to normal operation. Threats and challenges for services can range from simple misconfiguration to targeted attacks.

Resilient computing is a form of failover that distributes redundant implementations of IT resources across physical locations. IT resources can be pre-configured so that if one becomes deficient, processing is automatically handed over to another redundant implementation. Within cloud computing, the characteristic of resiliency can refer to redundant IT resources within the same cloud (but in different physical locations) or across multiple clouds. Cloud consumers can increase both the reliability and availability of their applications by leveraging the resiliency of cloud-based IT resources, (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: A resilient system in which Cloud B hosts a redundant implementation of Cloud Service A to provide failover in case Cloud Service A on Cloud A becomes unavailable. (whatiscloud, 2017)

The core persistent data stores are particularly challenging with respect to resiliency and high availability. While databases implemented on physically proximate equipment have well understood clustering solutions that retain transactional integrity by synchronizing duplicate data stores, distributed large-scale databases often require more thoughtful design. This can range from asynchronous replication of data to avoid latency in the transaction flow to data partitioning and the adoption of an “eventually consistent” paradigm for the underlying data. The specifics of the solution will depend on the application design and any requirements to limit data loss (Recovery Point Objective or RPO), but there are well understood engineering patterns that accommodate common needs.

A larger concern with distributed systems resiliency is organization. All infrastructure environments manage multi-layered resilience complexity with a mix of vendor and in-house engineering. A typical non-cloud environment can leverage a more mature marketplace for vendor products and services facilitating the various layers. Resiliency in cloud environments may require more in-house engineering and less mature technologies to meet performance and availability goals for the applications or services. This often entails additional risk or organizational change to support the application. The trend toward creating a more synergistic relationship between applications engineering and systems administrators is one key indicator of how these changes are playing out in the enterprise.

While moving applications into a private or public cloud environment may present an opportunity to save costs or improve operations, applications vary in their suitability for cloud infrastructures. Some architectures (web farms, application server clusters, etc) are

similar to cloud native best practice, and require little retooling to allow for resiliency. More complex patterns are also manageable with proper planning, design, and execution. Evaluating applications explicitly for resiliency requirements and fit against cloud native architectural principles allows firms to take best advantage of cloud economics and efficiencies in the enterprise.

2.2 Security Threats in the Cloud Computing Systems

This section illustrates several common security attacks (intrusions), which limits availability, confidentiality and integrity issues to Cloud resources and services. These include:

2.2.1. Insider attack

The person who could access the whole information system with privileged authority is defined as *insider*. Insider attacks are organized and performed by these individuals to destroy or manipulate the knowledge about system or providers and include every kind of attacks which can possibly be executed from inside. Authorized Cloud users may attempt to misuse unauthorized privileges. Insiders may commit frauds and destroy information or they may disclose information to others. This poses a serious trust issue. (Farzad, 2011).

2.2.2. Flooding attack

In this type of attack, attackers can send very large amounts of packets from exploited information resources, and they are called as zombie (innocent host). Here, attacker tries to flood victim by sending huge number of packets from innocent host (*zombies*) in network. Packets can be either one of TCP, ICMP, UDP or a mix of these protocols. These kinds of attacks are mostly realized over unauthorized network connections. Because of cloud computing paradigms' nature, connections to the virtual machines are established everywhere over Internet. For this reason, exposition of cloud users with *Denial of Service (DoS)* and *Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS)* attacks are inevitable. Flooding attacks affect the availability of serviced for authorized users. An attack that is realized to a server which serves one kind of service can prevent a vast of scale accessibility to this served service. These kinds of attacks are called DoS attacks. If servers' resources are slogged after flooding attacks and it prevents the execution of other services, which run on the server, this kind of attacks are called indirect DoS attacks. (Farzad, 2011).

2.2.3. User to Root attacks

In this type of attack, an intruder seizes the account and password information of an authorized user, and he can acquire limitless access to the whole system. This makes him able to exploit vulnerabilities for gaining root level access to system. For example; Buffer overflows are used to generate root shells from a process running as root. Buffer overflows are used for establish console connection for authorized processes. This type of intrusion can be realized with writing an excessive amount of data to a statically defined buffers' capacity, and the information is captured by intruders from this overflowed data. An attacker who owned the account and password information of an authorized user can hold the access privilege to servers and also to virtual machines. (Farzad, 2011).

2.2.4. Port Scanning

An attack that identifies open, closed and filtered ports on a system. Through port scanning, attackers can find open ports and attack on services running on these ports. Network related details such as IP address, MAC address, router, gateway filtering, firewall rules etc. can be

known through this attack. Various port scanning techniques are TCP scanning, UDP scanning, SYN scanning, FIN scanning, ACK scanning, Window scanning (same as ACK scan but it checks any modifications in the window field of packet) etc. Port scanning is not used by its own, an intruder realizes the actual attack after getting information about open ports and running services. (Farzad, 2011).

2.2.5 Attacks on Virtual Machine (VM) or hypervisor

After compromising hypervisor, control of the virtual machines in the virtual environment will be captured. Zero day attacks are one of the methods that attack virtual machines and use hypervisor or other virtual machines to attack other virtual machines. A zero day vulnerability is a threat that tries to exploit application vulnerabilities that are unknown to others or the software developer. Zero day attacks use known vulnerabilities before system or software developers apply patches or updates. Multiple virtual machines use the same resource pool, especially hardware and with this kind of access side channel data has a chance to be captured, which flow one virtual machine to other. A zero-day vulnerability was exploited in the HyperVM virtualization application which resulted in destruction of many virtual servers based websites.

2.2.6 Backdoor channel attacks

It is a passive attack which allows hackers to gain remote access to the infected node in order to compromise user confidentiality. Using backdoor channels, hackers can control victim's resources and can make it as *Zombie* to attempt DDoS attack. It can also be used to disclose the confidential data of victim. Due to this, compromised system faces difficulty in performing its regular tasks. In Cloud environment, attacker can get access and control Cloud user's resources through backdoor channel and make VM as *Zombie* to initiate DoS/DDoS attack. For insider attacks, signature based intrusion detection solutions can normally be used. To prevent attacks on VM/Hypervisor, anomaly based intrusion detection techniques can be used. For flooding attack and backdoor channel attack, either signature based intrusion detection or anomaly based intrusion detection techniques can be used. Firewall (in Cloud) could be the common solution to prevent some of the attacks listed above.

3.0 Security Principles in the Cloud

This section of the Cloud Security Guidance summarises the essential security principles to consider when evaluating cloud services, and why these may be important to your organisation. Some cloud services will fulfil all of the security principles, while others only a subset.

Consumers of cloud services should decide which of the principles are important, and how much (if any) assurance they require in the implementation of these principles.

Providers of cloud services should consider these principles when presenting their offerings to public sector consumers. This will allow consumers to make informed choices about which services are appropriate for their needs.

The Cloud Security Principles are summarised in the table below.

Table 1: Cloud Security Principle

Cloud Security Principle	Description	Why this is important
1. Data in transit protection	Consumer data transiting networks should be adequately protected against tampering and eavesdropping via a combination of network protection and encryption.	If this principle is not implemented, then the integrity or confidentiality of the data may be compromised whilst in transit.
2. Asset protection and resilience	Consumer data, and the assets storing or processing it, should be protected against physical tampering, loss, damage or seizure.	If this principle is not implemented, inappropriately protected consumer data could be compromised which may result in legal and regulatory sanction, or reputational damage.
3. Separation between consumers	Separation should exist between different consumers of the service to prevent one malicious or compromised consumer from affecting the service or data of another.	If this principle is not implemented, service providers cannot prevent a consumer of the service affecting the confidentiality or integrity of another consumer's data or service.
4. Governance framework	The service provider should have a security governance framework that coordinates and directs their overall approach to the management of the service and information within it.	If this principle is not implemented, any procedural, personnel, physical and technical controls in place will not remain effective when responding to changes in the service and to threat and technology developments.
5. Operational security	The service provider should have processes and procedures in place to ensure the operational security of the service.	If this principle is not implemented, the service can't be operated and managed securely in order to impede, detect or prevent attacks against it.
6. Personnel security	Service provider staff should be subject to personnel security screening and security education for their role.	If this principle is not implemented, the likelihood of accidental or malicious compromise of consumer data by service provider personnel is increased.
7. Secure development	Services should be designed and developed to identify and mitigate threats to their security.	If this principle is not implemented, services may be vulnerable to security issues which could compromise consumer data, cause loss of service or enable other malicious activity.
8. Supply chain security	The service provider should ensure that its supply chain satisfactorily supports all of the security principles that the	If this principle is not implemented, it is possible that supply chain compromise can undermine the security of the service and affect the

	service claims to implement.	implementation of other security principles.
9. Secure consumer management	Consumers should be provided with the tools required to help them securely manage their service.	If this principle is not implemented, unauthorised people may be able to access and alter consumers' resources, applications and data.
10. Identity and authentication	Access to all service interfaces (for consumers and providers) should be constrained to authenticated and authorised individuals.	If this principle is not implemented, unauthorised changes to a consumer's service, theft or modification of data or denial of service may occur.
11. External interface protection	All external or less trusted interfaces of the service should be identified and have appropriate protections to defend against attacks through them.	If this principle is not implemented, interfaces could be subverted by attackers in order to gain access to the service or data within it.
12. Secure service administration	The methods used by the service provider's administrators to manage the operational service should be designed to mitigate any risk of exploitation that could undermine the security of the service.	If this principle is not implemented, an attacker may have the means to bypass security controls and steal or manipulate large volumes of data.
13. Audit information provision to consumers	Consumers should be provided with the audit records they need to monitor access to their service and the data held within it.	If this principle is not implemented, consumers will not be able to detect and respond to inappropriate or malicious use of their service or data within reasonable timescales.
14. Secure use of the service by the consumer	Consumers have certain responsibilities when using a cloud service in order for this use to remain secure, and for their data to be adequately protected.	If this principle is not implemented, the security of cloud services and the data held within them can be undermined by poor use of the service by consumers.

4.0 Threat Detection Best Practices – IDS (Intrusion Detection System)

The most common threat detection techniques used by the cloud are based on signatures of known attacks and behaviour of users (Cloonan, 2017). However, in order to improve the performance of IDS, it is better to use a combination (hybrid) of these techniques.

Figure 2: Intrusion detection techniques (Liao, 2013).

4.1 Signature Based Detection

Signature based detection is performed by comparing the information collected from a network or system against a database of signatures. A signature is a predefined set of rules or patterns that correspond to a known attack. This technique is also known as misuse detection. It can efficiently detect known attacks with negligible false alarms. Signature based method helps network managers with average security expertise to identify intrusions accurately. It is a flexible approach since new signatures can be added to database without modifying existing ones. However, it is unable to detect unknown attacks. (Liao, 2013).

In Cloud environment, signature based intrusion detection method can be utilized at front-end (that is host) of cloud for detection of known attacks from external network. It can also detect both internal and external intrusions if deployed at back end (that is processing servers) of cloud. However, it is unable to identify unknown attacks in cloud just like traditional networks (Mazzariello et al., 2010, Bakshi et al., 2010).

4.2 Anomaly Based Detection

Anomaly based detection compares current user activities against preloaded profiles of users on networks to detect abnormal behaviour that may be intrusions. The profiles may be dynamic or static and correspond to the expected or benign behaviour of users. To build a profile, regular activities of users, network connections, or hosts are monitored for a specific period of time called *training period*. Profiles are developed using various features like failed login attempts, number of times a file is accessed by a particular user over a particular time duration, CPU usage etc. Anomaly based detection is effective against unknown attacks. An attack detected by anomaly based technique can be used as a signature in signature based detection. However, it produces a large number of false alarms due to irregular network and user behaviour. Moreover, it also requires large data sets to train the system for normal user profiles. A common example of anomaly based detection is the extra security questions raised by most email service providers whenever there is a login attempt from a strange device or user's location.

4.3 Hybrid Detection

The efficiency of IDS can be significantly improved by combining signature based and anomaly based techniques which is called Hybrid detection technique. The motivation behind this combination is the ability to detect both known and unknown attacks using signature based and anomaly based detection techniques. In cloud computing, Modi et al (2012) have used hybrid detection techniques to increase the efficiency of IDS.

5.0 Cloud Resilience Best Practice

Cloud computing businesses rely on infrastructure and services delivered through the internet. But there are many risks facing this business such as they are vulnerable to network outages. Cloud Resilience must cut across all the architectural layers which are infrastructure as a service (IaaS), platform as a service (PaaS) and software as a service (SaaS).

According to Buecker et al (2014), the resiliency building block is decomposed into six building blocks, thus helping with the implementation of a highly resilient solution:

1. Data resiliency:

- Allows services to specify the tolerable data loss in the case of failure.
- Used to determine an appropriate replication strategy for data (examples include synchronous, asynchronous, and backup).
- Initiates various types of replication sessions and manages these for consistency and link failure detection.
- Initiates a point in time backup of data at given frequencies.

2. Configuration for resiliency:

- Defines the goals to reach and define technologies, configurations and resiliency policies
- Includes targets for recovery time in either qualitative or quantitative measures, required levels of redundancy for various components and percentage of uptime
- Determines how often policies are expected to change, and the points of variability

3. Resiliency monitoring and management:

- Availability monitoring of systems and services includes detection mechanisms to determine failures, potential failures, and changes in configuration that may have an impact on maintaining the resiliency policy
- Configuration change assessment will analyse the identified configuration change and determine what (if any) impact this change will have on meeting resilience policy
- Failure assessment evaluates failures and predicted failures in the environment to determine impacted components, degree of impact, scope of impact and effect on the resiliency policy specifications as a result of the impact.

4. Availability and continuity management:

- Instantiates cloud-managed service resiliency patterns to maintain established level of resiliency
- Defines options for availability configuration at different service level objectives (SLO) of databases or server environments, and a myriad of other configurations and settings
- Uses resiliency tiers to classify business resilience requirements into a set of consistent metrics and criteria across an organization

5. Resiliency policy management:

- Uses Policy Authoring to describe the capability to add, edit and delete policies relating to resiliency
- Centralization or de-centralization of policy management
- Policy distribution describes how aspects of a given resilience policy will be made available to the various managed component
- Policy evaluation will be determined based on policy content and level of distribution

6. Resiliency compliance management:

- Tracks, audits and reports the compliance status of resiliency targets
- Monitors the resiliency targets and the level of resiliency being achieved by the cloud infrastructure
- Identifies where there are noncompliant conditions
- Audit of compliance provides a history of on-going achievement of resiliency targets

6.0 Conclusion

The cooperation of threat knowledge (known attacks and unknown threats), among cloud administrators within the enterprise network or with other cloud services providers will contribute to better incident detection and prevention. This enhances cloud security and provides faster and more effective incident response and the “come-alive time” whenever there is network down-time will be incredibly fast thereby improving business profit for service providers.

Some architectures (web farms, application server clusters) are similar to cloud native best practice, and require little retooling to allow for resiliency. More complex patterns are also manageable with proper planning, design, and execution. Evaluating applications explicitly for resiliency requirements and fit against cloud native architectural principles allows firms to take best advantage of cloud economics and efficiencies in the enterprise.

7.0 Recommendation

Since cloud computing is a highly promising trend in the world of computing, service provider should not compromise security, availability and resilience for anything. Adequate security measures should be embarked upon and a framework to provide proactive intrusion

detection which is applicable to the Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) cloud service model. This model is the foundation for cloud services and any security breach at this level will inevitably compromise the upper cloud service layers (e.g. PaaS and SaaS).

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